

MODIFICATION OF CIVILIZATION TO MODERNIZATION

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Modification of Civilization to Modernization

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BACKGROUND

There are 197 countries in the world. Every country has its own norms, values and culture [Matters, 2008]. Pakistan being muslim country is famous for its rich culture based on humanity and integrity. Life style of its people is based on Islamic principles. Unfortunately with the passage of time ethical standards of the people of this country has been replaced by materialistic things. It has been observed that in last two decades the priorities of people has been changed. Formerly people prefer to help others who are in need of financial assistance but now the demand and love for materialistic things has been increased to an extent that financially stable people are reluctant to help poor and needy persons. The competition with fellow and people of their social network compel them to purchase luxurious items so to maintain their social status. Maintenance of social status is considered more important than provision of basic need of life to poor people. In earlier time the main aim of life was performance of good deeds so as to establish a harmonious society and set role model for new generation.

IDEA

The people of earlier time were self-disciplined and they were aware about accountability for their deeds on the day of judgment. Now the main concern of people has been changed. Non-realistic attitude has been opted by maximum number of people. Good action has been limited to shooting of video of an unacceptable behavior. Injustice, barbarism and violence are condemn through conducting walk, holding of play cards, burning of candles and through exchange of hard talk on television talk show or social

media. Shooting of violence scene or any other incident instead of helping the victim has become a common practice. People are incapable to take responsibility of being active member of society. Their role in development of sound and healthy society is negligible due to modification of their mind set. People are reluctant to take practical step against injustice and violence.

IMPLEMENTATION

Not It's time to shift back to the norms and value on which society of this country was established. The value of self-responsibility and self-accountability need to be rejuvenated. The people should be encouraged to lead simple life. Their love for luxurious and materialistic things needs to be minimized, so as to reduce the imbalance in the society. One things that is common among most of the people of Pakistan is that they are blind follower of others culture that is propagated in their lives through media. Therefore, programs presented on media may also be streamlined on the principle of simplicity.

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